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BEE HEALTH BIOMARKERS: EFFECTS OF ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIONS

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Abstract

While foraging, bees are exposed to anthropogenic actions in their environment, which leads to the weakening of their colonies^{1,2}. The damage to these colonies reflects sub-lethal changes that are measurable at the molecular, biochemical, cellular, or physiological levels, collectively called biomarkers^{1,2,3}. Organisms from the species *Melipona mandacaia* were collected from three areas with different anthropogenic pressures in Casa Nova – BA and Petrolina – PE, Brazil. The areas were: i) a natural Caatinga area with no anthropogenic pressure; ii) a rural area close to Caatinga with low anthropogenic pressure; and iii) an urban region with high anthropogenic pressure.

The enzymatic biomarkers related to neurotransmission (acetylcholinesterase - AChE), antioxidant response (catalase - CAT), detoxification pathways (glutathione S-transferases - GST), and membrane damage through the quantification of lipid peroxidation (LPO) levels were measured in organisms from all the areas. Results indicated that AChE activity was significantly higher in bees from less disturbed areas, while urban bees exhibited elevated GST activity, highlighting the stressors associated with urbanisation. Notably, the bees from the urban area exhibited higher CAT activity than those from natural areas, indicating a possible compensatory response to environmental stress caused by anthropogenic factors present in the urban environment or any immunological response. Despite the proximity to anthropogenic influences, lipid peroxidation levels did not differ significantly across treatments, indicating resilience in the antioxidant system. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that *Melipona mandacaia* bees demonstrate significant variations in enzymatic biomarker activity depending on the degree of environmental disturbance. This reinforces the importance of biomarkers in assessing anthropogenic impacts and conserving bee colonies across different ecosystems.

References

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